

DIRECTIONS D1.2:

Report on risk-based and
asymmetrical operation of offshore
HVDC grids

June 2026

This deliverable forms part of the DIRECTIONS project, funded by the Energy Transition Funds, FOD Economy, Belgium.
Contributors: G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem and H. Ergun.

With the support from:

Contents

1	Executive summary	1
2	Introduction and motivation	5
3	Topology optimization model	7
4	Identification of relevant metrics for busbar splitting	11
4.1	Introduction and motivation	11
4.2	Identified metrics	13
4.2.1	Metric design	13
4.2.2	Evaluation, testing and validation	14
4.2.3	Testing the metrics with a 118-bus test case	14
4.2.4	Validating the metrics with 793-bus test case	15
5	Grid topology optimization under renewable energy sources' forecast uncertainty	19
5.1	Introduction and motivation	19
5.2	Intuition behind the multistep & stochastic grid topology optimization model	22
5.2.1	Topology optimization workflow	22
5.2.2	Renewables Energy Sources' uncertainty quantification and time series	23
5.3	Results recap for a 14-day-long simulation in a hybrid AC/DC 50-bus test case	26
6	Grid topology optimization applied to the asymmetrical operation of full bipolar HVDC links in hybrid AC/DC grids	29
6.1	Introduction and motivation	29
6.2	Optimization model	30
6.3	Test case description	30
6.4	Results	31
7	Discussion and conclusion	35

Chapter 1

Executive summary

The governments of nine countries in the North Sea have committed to deploying at least 300 GW of offshore wind capacity in the North Sea area by 2050. Delivering this power to shore will require interconnected High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) grids linking offshore electrical energy hubs (EEHs) to onshore networks. These multi-terminal HVDC systems introduce significant planning and operational challenges, and grid congestion has already reached record costs, e.g, exceeding €2.7 billion in Germany alone in 2024. This deliverable addresses how a more effective use of existing grid infrastructure, through topology optimisation models including a quantification of the inherent risk related to renewable energy sources (RES), can alleviate congestion and reduce total generation costs while waiting for new grid expansion projects. Building on the grid topology optimisation model with busbar splitting (BuS) developed in DIRECTIONS D1.1, this report extends the methodology in three directions.

Key Contributions

Pre-Screening Metrics for Busbar Splitting Applying busbar splitting to every node in a large transmission grid is computationally intractable, as each additional candidate exponentially increases problem complexity. This deliverable proposes three lightweight metrics, computable from standard AC optimal power flow results, to identify the small subset of busbars where splitting is most likely to reduce generation costs:

- Φ (**phi**): Sum of absolute Locational Marginal Price differences across all branches connected to a busbar. Busbars with high ϕ values sit at zone boundaries where topological actions can reroute flows and reduce congestion.
- ξ (**xi**): Number of congested branches incident to a busbar, flagging locations with uneven branch utilisation.

- **ζ (zeta):** Presence of binding voltage angle or magnitude constraints, which acts as a negative filter: busbars subject to these limits are unlikely to benefit from splitting.

Validated on test cases of 118 and 793 buses, the metrics successfully identified 3 of the 4 highest-value splitting candidates in the larger system, while reducing total computation time from over 19 hours (exhaustive search) to under 1 hour. This makes the approach practical for real system operators.

Grid Topology Optimisation Under Renewable Forecast Uncertainty Topological actions to minimize generation costs are decided day-ahead before real-time operation, yet renewable energy forecasts still carry significant forecast errors. Belgian offshore wind data from 2024 demonstrates that measured output can deviate substantially from day-ahead forecasts, particularly at low and high capacity factors. Therefore, optimising the grid topology based solely on a deterministic forecast can result in sub-optimal or costly outcomes when actual generation differs. This deliverable introduces a multistep stochastic optimisation model that addresses this by:

- Optimising topology across a 24-hour horizon, including operational constraints on the frequency of switching actions.
- Representing forecast uncertainty through a set of scenarios generated via K-means clustering on a real forecast error probability density function, balancing representativeness against computational tractability.
- Proposing flexible models for system operators, from hourly topology switching to a fixed daily topology or a limited number of switching actions per day.

Tested on a hybrid AC/DC 50-bus system over a 14-day simulation, the scenario-based approach outperforms or replicates the deterministic day-ahead forecast approach in total costs (generation plus redispatch). Using 6 to 8 scenarios was found to capture most of the available benefit. In addition, all optimised topologies passed nonlinear AC feasibility checks, confirming that the LPAC approximation used in optimisation yields AC-OPF feasible solutions.

Busbar Splitting for Asymmetrical Operation of Bipolar HVDC Links Full bipolar HVDC links, such as the 2 GW, 525 kV standard proposed by TenneT, can operate asymmetrically when one pole is offline due to a fault or maintenance. In offshore environments, such outages can persist for days or weeks, making it economically interesting to operate the healthy pole as

efficiently as possible to maximize the power transfer through it. This deliverable demonstrates that splitting the AC busbars to which HVDC converters are connected can reduce total generation costs for a given test case. By placing the two converter poles on different sections of a split busbar, previously binding voltage constraints are relaxed and decoupled, resulting in a chance to dispatch cheaper generators. On a 15-bus test case, splitting busbars reduced total generation costs up to 18.3% compared to the base case optimal power flow. The main limitation is the small test case size, necessitated by the mixed-integer nonlinear nature of the problem. Scaling to larger meshed HVDC systems with different optimal power flow formulations is identified as the principal direction for future work.

Overall Findings

The central finding of this deliverable is that busbar splitting yields meaningful cost reductions at only a limited number of locations in any given network, but the savings at those locations can be substantial. The three contributions work together: the pre-screening metrics make the search tractable, the stochastic multistep model ensures that topology decisions are robust to renewable forecast uncertainty, and the asymmetric operation of HVDC grids extension shows that topological flexibility remains valuable even under stressed operating conditions, such as in the case of a pole fault. Together, these tools provide system operators with practical, computationally feasible methods for identifying and implementing effective remedial actions in future hybrid AC/DC grids with high renewable penetration.

This deliverable's content is based on the following papers:

- G. Bastianel, J. Kircheis, M. Van Deyck, D. Lee, G. Chaffey, M. Vanin, H. Ergun, J. Beerten, and D. Van Hertem, "Review, definition and challenges of electrical energy hubs", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 226, p. 116258, 2026.
- G. Bastianel, M. Vanin, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "Optimal Transmission Switching and Busbar Splitting in Hybrid AC/DC Grids.", *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 2026, 102182, ISSN 2352-4677, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2026.102182>.
- G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, H. Ergun, L. Roald, "Day-ahead transmission grid topology optimization considering renewable energy sources'uncertainty", *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, Volume 174, 2026, 111527, ISSN 0142-0615, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2025.111527>.
- G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, H. Ergun, and L. Roald, "Identifying Best Candidates for Busbar Splitting.", arXiv:2510.13000, 2025. Accepted for publication at PSCC 2026.
- G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem and H. Ergun, "Assessing the Economic Value of AC-Side Busbar Splitting in Asymmetrical HVDC Grid Operation". Accepted for publication at the IET Conference Proceedings, 2026.

Chapter 2

Introduction and motivation

In 2023, the governments of Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, Denmark, France, Ireland, Luxembourg, Norway, and the United Kingdom have agreed on reaching at least 300 GW of offshore wind capacity installed in the North Sea by 2050 in the Esbjerg (2022) [1], Ostend (2023) [2] and Hamburg (2026) [3] North Sea summits. The power generated by offshore renewable energy sources (RES) can be collected in electrical nodes and transmitted to the onshore grid through interconnected high voltage direct current (HVDC) links, creating a multiterminal HVDC (MTDC) grid. These grids facilitate power exchange between different control areas without congesting the existing AC grid and will likely become considerably more common in the future [4, 5]. When combining this interconnection aspect with multi-GW generation in a single unit such as in the recent pioneering “*energy island*” or “*electrical energy hubs*” (EEHs) projects [6–9], several technical challenges emerge. These challenges, together with methodologies to tackle them, are discussed in detail in two publications emerging from the DIRECTIONS project [9, 10]. To keep the text concise, these challenges are shown in Figure 2.1, but the interested reader is referred to [9, 10] to have their thorough description.

This deliverable focuses on the steady-state planning and operations of EEHs, and specifically on the **risk** related to RES forecast in grid topology optimization and on asymmetrical operations of HVDC bipolar links in hybrid AC/DC grids. Therefore, this deliverable is based on the grid topology optimization model with busbar splitting defined in the DIRECTIONS deliverable D1.1 and published in [11] to consider the aspects of:

- Selection of relevant areas in a power grid where to apply busbar splitting through the identification of efficient metrics.
- Including renewable energy sources’ day-ahead forecast uncertainty in the grid topology optimization.

Figure 2.1: Shortlisting of technical challenges related to electrical energy hubs [9]. The challenges are related to three different categories, namely power system control, planning, and protection.

- Grid topology optimization applied to the asymmetrical operation of full bipolar HVDC links in hybrid AC/DC grids.

The next chapter recaps the planning methodology from deliverable D1.1, i.e., the grid topology optimization model to minimize the total generation costs in the system while changing the grid topology through busbar splitting under different operating conditions. Chapter 3 couples this model with the identification of some metrics to select relevant busbars for busbar splitting while basing on optimal power flow results. Moreover, chapter 4 includes RES' forecast uncertainty in the grid topology optimization model, while chapter 5 extends the work in [12] to include busbar splitting of both AC and DC busbars in the asymmetrical operation of full bipolar HVDC links in hybrid AC/DC grids. The final chapter reflects on how the discussed models can be applied to a variety of realistic test cases.

Chapter 3

Topology optimization model

The proposed planning methodology consists of selecting the optimal topology among a set of possible configurations for a given set of system layouts. The principle of the method shown in Figure 3.1 outlines the steps to select the final topology. By using layout and configuration information as input, and optimising the topology for a number of different credible operating states, we can compare layouts and their corresponding configurations in terms of operational benefits, allowing us to make a robust investment decision. The heart of the methodology is an optimization model (and tool) developed as part of *DIRECTIONS* - Task 1.1. The full mathematical description of the model and its implementation is published in [11] and is online available under [this link](#).

Figure 3.1: Steps of the planning methodology described in the deliverable.

As the busbar splitting (BuS) model will be extended in the next chapter of the deliverable, we explain the rationale behind the model qualitatively. Fig. 3.2 provides an example of a busbar with two branches, a generator and a load.

To represent BuS actions for busbar i in Fig. 3.2 (left), we remove all grid elements connected to the busbar and instead connect them to new auxiliary busbars. Then, the original bus is split into two buses i and i' . For each

component, we introduce a pair of switches sw_{vmi}^{ac} and $sw_{\kappa mi'}^{ac}$ to represent which part of the split busbar the component can be connected to. Each component cannot be connected to more than one bus, but can be completely disconnected. We also introduce a binary variable $sw_{ZILii'}^{ac}$ to represent the open/close status of the busbar coupler, which connects the busbars i and i' . If the busbar coupler $sw_{ZILii'}^{ac}$ is closed, the two parts of the AC busbar are connected, and AC buses i and i' have the same voltage angle and magnitude values.

Figure 3.2: Steps behind the topology optimization model proposed in [11, 13]. The selected busbar i (left) is split into two buses i and i' , connected through a busbar coupler $ZIL_{ii'}$. The open/close position of this busbar coupler $ZIL_{ii'}$ is represented in the optimization model by a binary variable. Each network element that was connected to busbar i in the input topology is linked to an auxiliary bus (named m , n , o and p in the figure) and can be connected to either one (i) or the other part (i') of the split busbar through a switch (center). Each switch is also represented in the model through a binary variable. After the optimization, the inactive switches are removed to yield the new topology (right).

The following paragraphs outline the input data that is used in the topology optimiser to determine the operational benefits for different layouts and configurations:

- **Layout and configuration inputs:** pre-determined layouts and configurations (a set of planning candidates) for optimising their topology under different operating conditions. The decision variables are represented by switching units, which can be open or closed.
- **Topology outputs:** the topology optimiser model outputs the status (open/closed) of the several switching units included in the pre-determined configurations used as inputs. Together with the status of the switching units, the power flow through the AC and DC branches of the hybrid AC/DC grids, the voltage magnitudes and angles, and the converter and generator set points for a given operating condition are com-

puted by the model for a specified objective, e.g., minimum generation (re)dispatch cost, minimum RES curtailment etc.

- **Input data - Operating conditions:** numerical parameters which are used by the model to compute the optimal value of all the variables in the model. The data used as input for the optimization model are:
 - **Generation costs:** each generator type is assigned a fixed cost per generated MWh. Overall, the model's objective is to minimize generation costs, i.e., the operational cost of the system. However, as generation costs are highly volatile and unpredictable with respect to the long-term future, the objective of the optimization is formulated as maximising the amount of renewable energy injection into the system, or minimising RES curtailment. For this purpose, a merit order of different generator types is created, which represents a hierarchy in the dispatch decisions in which renewables get the highest priority.
 - **Demand time series:** Generator dispatch and system topology are determined such that the demand in the system is met under all considered loading conditions. A possible example of such demand profiles is the hourly demand time series of ENTSO-E's Ten-Year Network Development Plan 2024, providing an hourly aggregated demand for each market zone in Europe, which is obtained from the dataset [14].
 - **RES time series:** Similar to demand, also renewable energy production time series needs to be considered to account for the variability of RES generation. In this respect, it is important that the correlation between available renewable generation and power demand due to weather conditions is considered in an accurate way. One source of such data is the ENTSO-E's TYNDP 2024 data [14] set, providing the hourly capacity factor for onshore wind, offshore wind, and solar PV for each market zone in Europe.
 - **Cross-border exchanges:** Especially when isolating a specific region of the power grid to do a detailed topological analysis, the power exchanges between neighbouring zones should be consistently modelled such that the net position of a given zone does not change after topological remedial actions are applied. One approach that can be used in the European context is to first compute interconnection flows on ENTSO-E's zonal model, including one node per market zone in Europe. When running the topological optimization model for selected market zones (for a tractable

solution), the net transfer capacities through the interconnecting lines can be fixed to the outcome of the zonal model.

- **Network data:** includes the layout, configuration, and impedance data of the existing network, which is extended by the different planning candidates considered (and compared). The input data model used within *DIRECTIONS* is described under [15] and [16].

Chapter 4

Identification of relevant metrics for busbar splitting

4.1 Introduction and motivation

Several initiatives in Europe [17] and the US [18, 19] aim to improve the utilization of existing grid infrastructure by actively optimizing and reconfiguring the network topology to mitigate congestion and maximize transfer capacity. However, the available topological actions, such as OTS and substation reconfiguration with BuS are often restricted to well-established, expert-driven measures that system operators have employed for decades, even though the power flows through transmission grids are rapidly changing. As a result, potentially effective topological actions remain unidentified, and systematic methodologies to discover them are yet to be established both in the industry and in scientific literature. In particular, while the most common topological actions in industry include substation reconfiguration through BuS, academic papers investigating topology optimization with BuS are relatively new, in part because BuS is computationally highly challenging. Every busbar considered in the topology optimization problem introduces a new degree of freedom and thus has the potential to reduce generation costs compared to a standard OPF by solving congestion, therefore allowing the cheaper generators to be used to their maximum rated power, but representing multiple possible splitting configurations requires the use of binary variables and thus adds significant computational complexity. For example, Figure 4.1 shows the exponential growth of the number of possible configurations for one busbar with n network elements connected to it.

When implementing topology optimization for larger grids, it is therefore necessary to pre-screen busbars to identify promising candidate busbars for BuS. This paper addresses this issue by proposing metrics to identify efficient topological actions in transmission grids based on the results of

Figure 4.1: The number of possible configurations for one busbar grows exponentially with the number of network elements n connected to the busbar ($3n + 1$, with the $+1$ referring to the original topology).

optimal power flow (OPF) simulations. Although several metrics have been proposed in the literature, no prior work has systematically assessed their effectiveness in identifying the most suitable busbars for applying topological actions through BuS. In a rapidly evolving power system, such metrics can support system operators in identifying new impactful topological actions, ultimately maximizing the grid’s power transfer capacity.

In particular, in previous work [11, 13], we observed that only certain busbars lead to a reduction in generation costs when only one busbar was allowed to be split at a time. However, if applied to a large system, having to exhaustively check all busbars adds a significant computational cost to the optimization problem. The goal in this chapter is therefore to describe proposed metrics to identify a small subset of busbars that will reduce generation cost if we optimize their topology. These busbars are selected a priori through the proposed metrics, based on the grid topology and on the results of the AC-OPF formulation.

Note that a thorough description of the identification, testing, and validation process of the metrics is thoroughly discussed in [20]. The following section will recap the main findings of the paper and their relevance to system operators.

4.2 Identified metrics

4.2.1 Metric design

When designing these metrics, we only use information that can be obtained with comparatively low computational effort, such as from direct analysis of the system topology, e.g., identifying the number of network elements connected to a busbar, or from solving an AC-OPF. We further take inspiration from the metrics already existing in the literature to identify candidate lines to be switched in OTS problems and busbars for splitting in BuS problems. Specifically, we consider the general idea of identifying buses that are associated with congestion, have large differences in LMP to neighboring buses, and where a significant number of elements are connected to the busbar. Based on this, we propose the following three metrics:

4.2.1.1 Metric ϕ – Sum of absolute LMP differences

This metric is defined as the sum of the absolute differences in LMPs $|\Delta_{LMP}|$ across all branches connected to the selected busbar. This metric rewards buses that have multiple, high Δ_{LMP} values and is inspired by *congestion zone identification*, Δ_{LMP} , and *# of elements connected to the selected busbar* metrics. If a busbar lies within a congestion zone, even if one of its branches exhibits a large Δ_{LMP} , the remaining connections are likely to have limited Δ_{LMP} values, thus limiting the value of BuS to reduce generation costs [21]. Moreover, the potential to find topological actions reducing the total costs increases with the number of elements connected to a busbar [22, 23]. Thus, busbars exhibiting large Δ_{LMP} values over multiple incident branches are promising candidates.

4.2.1.2 Metric ξ – Number of congested branches

This metric evaluates the loading of the branches incident to a busbar and identifies the number of congested branches, inspired by a combination of the *congestion zones identification* and *# of elements connected to the busbar* metrics. A significant disparity in utilization of branches connected to the same busbar indicates the presence of local bottlenecks, where one or more branches operate closer to their thermal limits while others remain underutilized. Such imbalances suggest opportunities for remedial actions to redistribute flows, alleviate congestion, and therefore reduce generation costs by trying to use the cheapest generators to their maximum capacity.

4.2.1.3 Metric ζ – Binding voltage angle and magnitude limits

While a majority of existing work on OTS and BuS metrics has only considered DC-OPF representations, we base our metrics and optimization on AC-OPF (and approximations thereof) that also include consideration of reactive power and voltage magnitudes. Specifically, the OPF includes voltage magnitude, voltage difference, and angle difference constraints for each branch. Branches with binding voltage magnitude or angle difference limits imply congestion and restricted power transfer capability. Identifying busbars connected by branches close to these operational limits highlights locations where topological actions can increase (or not) the grid transmission capacity.

4.2.2 Evaluation, testing and validation

To *evaluate* the metrics, we first solve an AC-OPF with the original topology to determine the generation costs. Then, we solve the LPAC-BuS model with one busbar selected for each run of the topology optimization model, and finally run an AC-OPF with the optimized topology as a feasibility check and to evaluate the cost reduction.

We use a *testing phase* where we leverage results from two small test systems to assess what combination of metrics effectively identifies the most relevant candidates for BuS. We first evaluate the results of enabling BuS for each busbar by computing both the metrics and the corresponding cost reduction for that busbar. Then, we leverage the results to find effective combinations of metrics. Since it is possible that we overfit our metrics to the specific test cases during the testing phase, we then implement a *validation phase*. In the validation phase, we apply the combination of metrics to two larger test cases and analyze their performance on this previously unseen data.

4.2.3 Testing the metrics with a 118-bus test case

Table 4.1 shows the value of the different proposed metrics as well as the cost reduction achieved with BuS for the buses with the highest ϕ -metric values (top) and busbars that lead to a cost decrease of $>0.05\%$, but are not in the top-10 ϕ -ranked busbars (bottom).

We observe that the busbars with high ϕ , many *connected branches/elements*, and without *binding voltage limits* (ζ) lead to a cost decrease compared to the AC-OPF. Importantly, 4 out of 5 busbars with a cost reduction larger than 0.1% are included among the busbars with the highest ϕ values. The highest cost decrease is for busbar 69, whose optimized topology is shown in Fig. 4.2. In this optimized topology, power can directly flow from busbar 49

Figure 4.2: Topology optimization model applied to busbar 69 in the *118-bus test case*. In the optimized topology, busbars 47 and 49 are decoupled from busbar 69 and the neighboring busbars, leading to a reduction in the total generation costs of 0.380% compared to the original AC-OPF.

to 47, as the branches connecting them are decoupled from the original busbar 69.

Among the buses in the bottom part of Table 4.1, we observe that busbars 80 and 42 are connected to several branches. The other busbars decrease cost by not reconnecting branches to the split busbar, essentially performing transmission line switching rather than BuS. They are therefore more complex to identify with our metrics. Finally, all the busbars with a cost decrease of $>0.05\%$ are within the first half of the 118 ϕ -ranked busbars, and two of them have ϕ above its average value of 219.13 [\$/MWh].

Note that for this test case, the entire optimization process took 214.7 s. Based on these results, we consider *busbars with several connected branches/elements* and a ϕ *above average* as metrics to select relevant busbars in the *validation* step.

4.2.4 Validating the metrics with 793-bus test case

We first select the 15 busbars with the highest ϕ -values and remove those with fewer than 4 elements connected to them. As a result, the 8 busbars on the top part of Table 4.2 are selected. Second, we select the 7 busbars with the highest # of *elements and branches connected to them*, and have a ϕ

Table 4.1: Metrics of the 10 busbars in the 118-bus test case with the highest sum of the absolute differences in LMPs over their branches (ϕ), and of the busbars with the highest cost decrease wrt AC-OPF, not in the top 10 ϕ -ranked busbars. Busbars at voltage limit (ζ) do not have a cost decrease, while there are limited congested ($> 85\%$ utilization) branches (ξ).

Busbar ID	ϕ [\$/MWh]	ϕ rank	# of branches	ξ [-]	# of elements	ζ [-]	% Cost decrease
69	2253.98	1	6	2	7	-	0.380
49	1836.24	2	12	1	14	-	0.344
100	1433.50	3	8	2	10	$U^m, 1.1$	0.000
59	1168.27	4	7	0	9	-	0.156
47	827.49	5	3	1	4	-	0.000
66	665.04	6	5	0	7	$U^m, 1.1$	0.000
103	570.94	7	4	1	6	-	0.039
56	559.88	8	6	0	8	-	0.017
65	552.91	9	4	0	5	-	0.000
77	509.41	10	7	0	9	-	0.132
80	371.05	19	8	0	10	-	0.143
42	326.99	22	4	0	6	-	0.098
44	115.77	57	2	0	3	-	0.097
45	192.69	41	3	0	4	-	0.091
43	206.29	37	2	0	3	-	0.064

higher than the mean ϕ value. These busbars are displayed on the bottom part of Table 4.2. We ensure that all the selected busbars are connected to at most one congested line (ξ -metric ≤ 1) and have no binding voltage angle or magnitudes constraints (ζ -metric = 0).

The rightmost column of Table 4.2 shows the cost decrease for the identified busbars. As for the 118-bus case, selecting busbars with high ϕ values and larger # of connected branches/elements leads to cost decreases for several busbars, namely 693, 470, 649, 171 and 23. At the same time, the 7 busbars selected using the # of branches/elements and ϕ values above the mean- ϕ lead to cost reductions as well.

To validate whether we identified the “best” busbars for splitting, we validate our results by splitting every busbar in the system and checking the cost reduction. Fig. 4.3 shows the results obtained by splitting one busbar at a time for all busbars in the 793-bus system. We observe that the proposed metrics identify 3 of the 4 busbars that lead to the largest reductions in generation costs, as well as several other buses with high cost reductions. We note that busbar 444, which yields the third-best cost reduction if split, has only two connected branches, both of which are utilized above 80% of their rated capacity (one at 100%). As with most busbars in the bottom part of the previous Table 4.1, not reconnecting a branch to the split busbar is leading to 444’s reduction in costs, suggesting that line switching rather than BuS is what achieves the cost reduction.

For this test case, splitting one busbar per time took 68102 s (19.14 h), 67639 s for the LPAC-BuS and 463.3 s for the AC-FC, while the total compu-

Table 4.2: Identification of 15 candidates for busbar splitting in the 793-bus test case with the proposed metrics, and related cost decrease. 12 optimized topologies out of 15 lead to a cost decrease in the AC-OPF.

Busbar ID	ϕ [\$/MWh]	ϕ rank	# of branches	ξ [-]	# of elements	% Cost decrease
693	2602.76	1	5	1	6	0.376
470	1630.23	2	3	1	4	0.650
406	1447.60	6	4	1	4	0.000
649	1230.62	9	4	0	5	0.274
677	1173.01	11	3	1	4	0.000
171	970.89	13	3	1	4	0.141
190	919.09	15	5	1	6	0.000
23	802.69	18	5	1	6	0.972
587	304.01	48	6	0	7	1.056
116	196.95	68	5	0	6	0.559
73	494.92	30	6	0	6	0.024
373	378.82	40	4	0	6	0.151
655	467.55	31	6	0	6	0.319
612	105.87	116	6	0	6	0.041
561	125.52	101	5	0	5	0.363

tational time to optimize only the the selected buses is considerably lower, with 3523.3 s (0.98 h).

The results show that our newly proposed ϕ -metric, defined as the *sum of the absolute differences in LMPs over the branches connected to a busbar (ϕ)*, in combination with the *# of elements connected to the busbar*, can help identify the busbars that achieve the highest cost reductions. Further, the presence of *binding voltage angle and magnitude limits (ζ -metric)* indicates that BuS will likely *not* reduce cost. Some of the buses that were not identified by our metrics achieved cost reductions through transmission line switching rather than BuS.

Given the flexibility of the proposed grid topology optimization model in including more than one busbar, future work will include testing combinations of busbars to achieve further reductions in generation costs, therefore assisting system operators in finding relevant areas for BuS in their grid. Consequently, the proposed metrics can be used on the grid planning side to investigate the possibility of retrofitting existing substations to effective topological actions when congestion takes place in the grid, or new substations or RES capacity are installed in the grid.

Figure 4.3: Cost decrease of the AC-OPF feasibility check for the optimized topology of the selected busbars compared to the results obtained by splitting one busbar at a time for the 793-bus test case. Most of the busbars selected with the identified metrics do lead to a reduction in generation costs. The busbars with the highest cost decreases tend to have a sum of the absolute differences in LMPs across the branches connected to them (ϕ) higher than the mean ϕ value.

Chapter 5

Grid topology optimization under renewable energy sources' forecast uncertainty

5.1 Introduction and motivation

Power grids have historically been expanded to maximise the power transfer capacity between the demand centres and bulk conventional power plants, with recurrent and *expected* power flows in the grid. Distributed large RES capacities cause variations in these recurrent power flows and potentially cause congestion in grids that were built without considering their distributed and fluctuating nature. As a result of these facts, the power grid is considered a bottleneck for the deployment of RES [24] and can lead to massive RES curtailment if it is not expanded efficiently [25].

In this regard, congestion costs have reached record-high numbers in recent years both in Europe [26] and the US [27], with Germany paying 2.774 bn€ in 2024 alone [28, 29], and all the US Independent System Operators accounted for 13.5 bn\$ in 2023 and 8.33 bn\$ in 2024 in the US [27, 30]. In addition, the global electricity demand is rapidly increasing [31], and further delaying urgent grid reinforcements would result in additional losses for the socioeconomic welfare [24, 25], and more GHGs emissions. Despite this urgent need for investments in the power grid, transmission projects are often delayed because of technical (supply chain issues, lack of workforce, lack of manufacturing capacity, bottlenecks with critical elements, etc. [32]) and non-technical (public opposition [33]) constraints.

The general idea of the initiatives mentioned in the previous Chapter [17, 18] is to use topological actions such as BuS and optimal transmission switching in more busbars to more effectively leverage existing grid infrastructure and reduce the need for expensive investments. However, these initiatives

are currently not dynamically employed for congestion management, and the available specific, predefined topological actions rely mainly on expert-based knowledge from the past. Particularly, the Core Capacity Calculation Process used by ENTSO-E [34] focuses on the use of non-costly remedial action optimization to maximize the available capacity for cross-zonal exchanges between each of the European electricity market zones, starting the optimization process from two days-ahead (D-2) until one day-ahead (D-1), before the electricity market is cleared. Considering the large RES penetration expected in the future, it is mandatory to include the inherent uncertainty in the RES forecast in the grid topology optimization process. For example, as shown in Fig. 5.1 plotted from wind measurements from the Open-DataElia platform from the Belgian Transmission System Operator (TSO) Elia [35], the difference in capacity factor between the measured value and the D-1 forecasted value at 11 am for the year 2024 can be considerable for a wide range of measured capacity factors.

Figure 5.1: Difference between the measured and forecasted D-1, 11 am capacity factor values for all the quarterly measured capacity factor in 2024 for the Belgian offshore wind farms, monitored capacity of 2.261 GW [35].

With an increased installed capacity, the difference between the measured and forecasted values might create imbalances in the grid, especially if the grid topology is optimized only considering the D-1 forecasted value for a large area. Therefore, as it will be shown later in the paper, considering the RES uncertainty in the grid optimization process helps to avoid using sub-optimal topologies while achieving economical benefits compared to the original topology.

Based on this discussion, there is a need for new optimization models that support system operators in evaluating the effect of topological actions while taking into account a longer time horizon (e.g. 24 hours) and the inherent uncertainty of renewable energy forecasts.

This Chapter and the related paper [13] seek to fill this gap by extending the steady-state grid topology optimization model for AC grids and hybrid AC/DC grids introduced in [11] in the following significant ways:

- First, we propose a multistep & stochastic optimization model which optimizes the topology for a period of hours, while considering scenarios to represent RES uncertainty. This model is based on the model in [11], but adds consideration of multiple time steps and RES uncertainty for the first time. We further propose several different versions of this model with different levels of flexibility:
 1. The first version of our model optimizes the grid topology hourly, without restrictions on the number of switching actions between time steps.
 2. The second version of our model selects a single optimal topology valid over a given time period.
 3. The third version of our model allows for a limited number of switching actions s_t in a given time period of 24 hours. The maximum number of switching actions S^{max} can be selected by the user.
- Second, we develop a methodology based on K-means clustering to quantify RES uncertainty through a small set of scenarios to be included in our scenario-based stochastic optimization. We apply this methodology to real forecasted offshore wind data used by TSOs [35].
- Third, we test the results obtained from the LPAC grid topology optimization model for feasibility with the nonlinear, non-convex “AC”-OPF formulation [15, 16] and run a continuous optimal redispatch model (with fixed topology) if the D RES capacity factor differs from the D-1 forecast. We find that the optimized topologies are always feasible when tested with the “AC”-OPF formulation.

We observe that the grid topology optimization models that consider the full day-ahead time series and multiple RES scenarios provide lower (or in some cases similar) cost when compared to the output of a deterministic model with BuS. As anticipated, providing more flexibility generally leads to lower costs. However, a *key contribution* of this Chapter and the related

paper [13] is to ensure that this more complex optimization model can be solved in a reasonable time, paving the way for application to larger systems.

5.2 Intuition behind the multistep & stochastic grid topology optimization model

One can study the topology optimization for only one of the two proposed dimensions, i.e., a single-step model ($T = 1$) with W scenarios or a multistep ($T > 1$) model with no stochasticity ($W = 1$). The possible different relations between hours and scenarios are summarised in Fig. 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Rationale behind the different formulations introduced in this paper. A multistep model (left) has > 1 timesteps t with 1 scenario w . The stochastic model (center) has 1 timestep t and W scenarios. The multistep & stochastic model (right) has T timesteps and W scenarios for each timestep t .

5.2.1 Topology optimization workflow

Figure 5.3 displays the workflow of the grid topology optimization model in the paper. After running the proposed models using the D-1 RES forecast, the optimized topology is tested for AC-OPF feasibility. At the time of realization D , the RES capacity factor is updated, and a redispatch model is run to compensate for eventual differences in the generator setpoints compared to the D-1 AC-OPF. For example, if the RES generation is lower than expected, a different generator has to increase its generation to ensure that the total generation matches the demand. The redispatch costs for each generator are assumed to be the marginal generation costs.

¹<https://github.com/Electa-Git/PowerModelsTopologicalActions.jl>

²<https://github.com/Electa-Git/StochasticPowerModelsTopologicalActions.jl>

Figure 5.3: Workflow for the grid topology optimization model presented in the paper

5.2.2 Renewables Energy Sources' uncertainty quantification and time series

As introduced in Fig. 5.1, plotting the quarterly difference between the D-1, 11 am wind capacity factor forecast value and the actual measured value from the Belgian Transmission System Operator Elia [35] for the year 2024, it is still a challenge for TSOs to provide a reliable D-1 forecast for the RES capacity factors in the power grid. This paper starts from this challenge to provide a scenario-based representation of the uncertainty based on the forecast error between the D-1, 11 am wind capacity factor forecast value and the actual measured value from [35]. While the uncertainty quantification is not the main goal of this Chapter, it is acknowledged that a considerable amount of work has been dedicated to selecting the best (number of) scenarios to quantify RES uncertainty for short-term grid operations [36–40]. While generally having a high number of scenarios helps to represent the probability distribution of RES uncertainty, the curse of dimensionality leads us to select a limited number of scenarios W to be used in this paper. To generate scenarios representing the RES forecast uncertainty, we follow several steps:

- *Analysis of the forecast error between the D-1, 11 am wind capacity factor forecast value and the actual measured value from [35]:* from Fig. 5.1 emerges that:
 - The biggest absolute differences take place when the measured value is low and the forecasted value is high.
 - With high measured capacity factors (above 0.9), the measured value is never severely underestimated. As the difference is contained within 0.0 and 0.6, the forecasted value is rarely higher than the measured one.

- With measured capacity factors higher than 0.75, the difference is contained between -0.8 (forecasted value \geq measured value) and 0.6 (measured value \geq forecasted value)
- *Computation of the wind uncertainty's probability density function (pdf):* the pdf of the difference between the measured and the D-1, 11 am forecasted value over the year can be computed with the Kernel Density Estimation method [41]³. The resulting pdf is shown in Fig. 5.4, its key features are:
 - The sharp peak at zero suggests a high frequency of small errors.
 - The heavy tails suggest that large errors are rare but more frequent than what a Gaussian distribution would suggest.
 - The asymmetry is minimal: the pdf is fairly symmetric around zero, but the length of the tails is different.

Figure 5.4: Pdf and related histogram of the difference between the measured and the D-1, 11 am forecasted value over the year 2024 from the EliaOpenData platform [35].

- *Generating samples and k-means clustering for creating the scenarios:* based on the pdf key features, we fit a Laplace (Double Exponential) distribution to represent the data in Fig. 5.4 and randomly generate 10^5 for each timestep. Then, a k-means clustering algorithm [42] is used to select k centroids of the randomly selected data, where k equals the number of scenarios w per timestep. The left-hand side of Figure 5.5

shows the capacity factors for two 24-hours long time series of a forecasted and measured value, and related scenarios. Note that while the scenarios cover a large uncertainty set around the forecasted value, the relative probability of each scenario w is computed based on the pdf shown in previous Fig. 5.4.

Two time series are selected to test the grid topology optimization model proposed in the paper. On the left-hand side of Fig. 5.5, a 24-hours long offshore wind time series with two peaks is used to investigate the value of grid topology optimization with high RES variability. Compared to the actual realization, the capacity factor is considerably overestimated at both the beginning and end of the day in D-1, 11 am forecasted value, while it is slightly underestimated from hour 12 to hour 19. The scenarios w computed through the methodology described in Section 5.2.2 cover a large spectrum of possible forecast errors. Note that each scenario has its own probability ω , and the sum of all the probabilities w for each timestep t equals 1. Moreover, the right-hand side of Fig. 5.5 shows 14 days of high wind with a 3-day dip in generation at the end of the first week. Even in this case, there is a considerable forecast error between the *Forecasted* and *Measured* values for several hours in the time series.

Figure 5.5: Time series used for the models developed in the paper. The measured (blue) and forecasted D-1, 11 am (yellow) capacity factors are shown for a day (left) and for two weeks (right). 8 scenarios w (light blue) are used to represent the uncertainty related to the forecasted value.

³The probability density function is computed using the two Julia packages KernelDensity.jl (<https://github.com/JuliaStats/KernelDensity.jl>) and Distributions.jl (<https://github.com/JuliaStats/Distributions.jl>).

5.3 Results recap for a 14-day-long simulation in a hybrid AC/DC 50-bus test case

In [13], the optimization are tested on modified versions of the IEEE 30-bus test case [43] and a 50-bus multi-terminal hybrid AC/DC grid, referred to as "case24_3zones_acdc.m" in [16]. The number of grid elements for both test cases is summarised in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Test cases used to test the proposed grid topology optimization models.

Test case	# Generators	# AC buses	# DC buses	#AC/DC conv	# AC branches	# DC branches
30-bus [43]	36	30	-	-	41	-
50-bus [16]	115	50	7	7	77	7

To keep the text concise, we focus primarily on the economic benefits of the presented models relative to total grid operating costs in the 50-bus hybrid AC/DC test case.

First, in the *Measured* time series, the grid topology optimization models lead to a reduction in generation costs of 0.02-0.04%, which is smaller than for the 30-bus test case, and in the vicinity of the 0.1% MIP gap. For the *Forecasted*, 6 and 8 time series, the reduction in total costs compared to their respective OPF is considerable, ranging from a minimum of 0.31 % in 6 to a maximum of 5.88% for the *Hourly BS of Forecasted*. The possibility of switching actions does not lead to additional cost reductions for the 6 and 8 time series, while it further reduces the costs for the *Forecasted* time series by 0.08%. As the generated scenarios already cover an extended range of forecast errors, the effect of additional switching actions does not bring additional economic benefits with this input data. Despite this, in this test case, using a scenario-based representation of the RES forecast uncertainty yields lower total costs than the *Forecasted* time series across all simulations, confirming the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. In the optimal power flow simulation, the grid topology optimization models of the 6 / 8 time series had sensibly higher costs than the *Forecasted* one. Therefore further refining the RES uncertainty quantification possibly guarantees lower costs than the *Forecasted* time series for a larger set of time instances.

Regarding the average simulation time for these 14 days simulations, they range from 0.33 s per hour (7.92 s per day) for the *Hourly BS* to 10397.70 s for the *Up to two switching action, Forecasted*.

Table 5.2: i) Increase in total costs (generation and redispatch) [%] compared to the *Measured* OPF value computed using the D measured offshore wind capacity, and ii) increase in total costs (generation and redispatch) [%] compared to the respective time series' OPF value for a 14-day simulation. Results are shown for the measured capacity factors at time D (*Measured*), the capacity factors of the D-1, 11 am forecast (*Forecasted*), and simulations with 6 and 8 scenarios *W*. The grid topology is optimized hourly (*Hourly BS*), once every 24 hours (*One topology*), or allowing up to one (*Up to one switching action*) or two switching actions (*Up to two switching actions*) for each time series. The total costs are the sum of the D-1 AC-OPF feasibility check and the redispatch models based on the measured D capacity factor.

Time series →	Measured	Forecasted		6 <i>W</i>		8 <i>W</i>	
Simulation ↓	% increase wrt Measured OPF	% increase wrt Measured OPF	% increase wrt Forecasted OPF	% increase wrt Measured OPF	% increase wrt 6 <i>W</i> OPF	% increase wrt Measured OPF	% increase wrt 8 <i>W</i> OPF
OPF	0	10.71	0	5.06	0	8.59	0
Hourly BS	-0.04	4.20	-5.88	3.68	-1.32	2.65	-5.47
One topology	-0.02	5.10	-5.07	4.74	-0.31	4.88	-3.41
Up to one switching action	-0.02	5.03	-5.13	4.74	-0.31	4.88	-3.41
Up to two switching actions	-0.02	5.03	-5.13	4.74	-0.31	4.88	-3.41

Chapter 6

Grid topology optimization applied to the asymmetrical operation of full bipolar HVDC links in hybrid AC/DC grids

6.1 Introduction and motivation

As mentioned in the previous chapters, HVDC offshore grids are proposed as a cost-effective solution to exchange and transmit offshore power to the onshore grid [44, 45], while reducing the pressure on onshore investments. Currently, 2 GW 525 kV full bipole point-to-point HVDC links [46] are proposed as a standard by TenneT [47], the Dutch-German Transmission System Operator, and this standard might be extended for Multi-Terminal and meshed HVDC grids. In bipoles, two poles are used at high DC voltage with opposite signs $\pm V_{dc}$. A conductor with low-impedance grounding is used as a Dedicated Metallic Return (DMR). Different from monopoles and rigid bipoles [46], full bipoles can be operated in an asymmetrical manner where both poles carry a different amount of power [12, 48, 49]. This is also the case for single pole (un)planned outages, where the link can be operated at half of its rating. Especially in offshore HVDC grids, maintenance and repair actions can limit the power transfer through a pole for days, if not weeks. Therefore, in a full bipole, the healthy pole can be used to transfer power. [12] proposed an optimal power flow (OPF) model to account for the asymmetrical operation of full bipoles in hybrid AC/DC grids, extending the OPF model for hybrid AC/DC grids presented in [16].

In this Chapter, we discuss the effectiveness of remedial actions in the asymmetrical operation of hybrid AC/DC grids, namely busbar splitting (BuS) of the AC busbar to which the AC/DC converters of an HVDC grid are

connected. As congestion costs have reached record-high numbers in recent years, both in Europe [26] and the US [27, 30], optimizing the grid topology through non-costly remedial actions, such as AC busbar splitting (BuS), has the potential to decrease the total generation costs in the power system [11].

Therefore, the *main contribution* of the Chapter is to show the economic benefit in terms of reduction in total generation costs brought by splitting AC busbars on a hybrid AC/DC grid with asymmetrical operation of the HVDC links. We achieve this goal by merging the asymmetrical OPF model for hybrid AC/DC grids developed in [12] and the grid topology optimization model from [11, 13], resulting in a mixed-integer nonlinear problem (MINLP) to optimize the topology of the AC busbar to which the AC/DC converters of an HVDC grid are connected. The optimization model is tested on a small 15-buses test case to show the potential of the methodology.

6.2 Optimization model

The grid topology optimization model through BuS implemented in [11, 13] is extended to the asymmetrical OPF model for hybrid AC/DC grids from [12] by adding detailed DC currents of a bipolar converter station with neutral point grounding, as presented in Fig. 6.1. For every converter c , the superscripts p and n indicate positive and negative poles, respectively, whereas r indicates the neutral, i.e, the direct metallic return (DMR). The reader is referred to [12] for a detailed description of all the constraints imposed on the DC currents.

6.3 Test case description

Given the complex mixed-integer nonlinear nature of the model, we test it on a small 15-bus test case (*case5_2grids_MC*) from [12], whose number of network elements is included in Table 6.1, and topology in Fig. 6.1. The DC grid in the 15-buses test case consists of 2 full bipole converters ($c = 1$ and $c = 2$, linked to the DC buses 1 and 2) and one symmetrical monopole ($c = 3$). As indicated in Fig. 6.1, the monopole condition is a consequence of a fault in the converter positive pole p . The per unit values of the terminal currents $I_{d\phi e\phi f\phi}^{dc}$ and of the power through each converter pole ρ coming from the OPF simulation are indicated in Fig. 6.1, too.

Figure 6.1: Visualization of the converter and conductor currents in the proposed model [12].

Table 6.1: Number of network elements in the 15-buses *case5_2grids_MC* test case from [12], used to validate the optimization models developed in this paper.

Test case	Generators	AC Buses	AC Branches	DC Buses	DC Branches	Loads
15-buses	5	11	14	4	3	9

6.4 Results

We select three case studies to evaluate the impact of splitting the AC busbar to which a converter is connected while the hybrid AC/DC grid is operated in an asymmetrical manner, i.e., the splitting of AC buses 2, 7, and both of them combined. Table 6.2 indicates the results of each case study, compared with the results of an OPF simulation, where no busbar splitting takes place. All three case studies lead to lower generation costs compared to the OPF simulation, with the case splitting busbars 2 and 7 having the highest cost reduction. For this reason, we select this case study to describe the effects of BuS more in-depth. The optimized topology is shown in Fig. 6.3, where both buses 2 and 7 are split, and the network elements linked to the original buses are connected to either one or the other part of the split busbar. In both cases, the two converter poles are not connected to the same part of the split bus, therefore allowing a more efficient power transmission through their ends. While the power directions stay the same as the OPF case in Fig. 6.2, less power is transferred through converters 1 and 2. The

Figure 6.2: 15-buses test case (*case5_2grids_MC*) from [12]. The per unit current ($I_{d^{\phi}e\phi}^{dc}$) values are indicated in black, while the power through each converter pole (ρ) is indicated in blue.

Table 6.2: Comparison of the results of the optimal power flow (OPF) and AC-busbar splitting (BuS) simulations on busbars 2 and 7, split singularly and combined.

optimization model	Split busbars	Objective value [\$ /h]	Benefit wrt OPF [%]	Time [s]	# Binary variables
OPF	-	869.094	-	2.506	-
BuS	2	756.465	12.959	25.195	17
BuS	7	806.844	7.163	71.025	17
BuS	2, 7	710.199	18.283	1133.000	34

reason behind this difference is that BuS on both buses 2 and 7 makes the voltage angle and magnitude constraints (M1.7) and (M1.8) on those buses nonbinding, giving a higher degree of freedom to the voltage-related decision variables on each part of the split buses, and therefore to the network elements originally connected to them. This is clearly shown in Figures 6.4, where the differences between voltage angles and magnitudes among *Bus 2 - Bus 2 - split* and *Bus 7 - Bus 7 - split* are considerable for the three case studies. Therefore, BuS guarantees a more efficient (cheaper) power transmission through the reconfiguration of the network elements' connections. As a result, grid congestion on the AC side is reduced, and cheaper generators 1 and 3 can increase their power set point, while the more expensive generator 2 produces less power, as shown in Fig. 6.5. Finally, this reconfiguration increases considerably the branch utilization of specific AC branches, such as AC branches 2 and 5 for the *Split bus 2* and *Split bus 2 & 7* simulations, and

Figure 6.3: Optimized topology of the 15-buses test case with busbar splitting on AC buses 2 and 7. The per unit current ($I_{d\phi e\phi f\phi}^{dc}$) values are indicated in black, while the power through each converter pole (ρ) is indicated in blue. In both buses, the two poles are connected to the two different parts of the split bus.

Figure 6.4: Voltage angles (left) and magnitudes (right) of buses 2, 7 and their split parts (*Bus 2 - split* and *Bus 7 - split*) for the optimal power flow (OPF), busbar splitting (BuS) on bus 2 (*Split bus 2*), BuS on bus 7 (*Split bus 7*), and BuS on buses 2 & 7 (*Split bus 2 & 7*) simulations.

AC branches 9, 12, and 14 for the *Split bus 7* and *Split bus 2 & 7* simulations, as indicated in Fig. 6.5.

Figure 6.5: Generator setpoints (left) and branch utilization (right) for the optimal power flow (OPF), busbar splitting (BuS) on bus 2 (*Split bus 2*), BuS on bus 7 (*Split bus 7*), and BuS on buses 2 & 7 (*Split bus 2 & 7*) simulations.

Chapter 7

Discussion and conclusion

This deliverable built on the grid topology optimization model with busbar splitting from D1.1, extending it in three directions: identifying relevant metrics to pre-screen busbars for splitting, incorporating RES forecast uncertainty into the optimization, and applying the optimization model to the asymmetric operation of full bipolar HVDC links in hybrid AC/DC grids.

Busbar splitting metrics The motivation for Chapter 4 is straightforward: applying busbar splitting to every busbar in a large transmission system to look for effective remedial actions is computationally intractable, since each additional busbar candidate introduces binary variables and exponentially increases the computational complexity of the problem. A pre-screening step is therefore necessary in practice. The three proposed metrics ϕ , ξ , and ζ are deliberately cheap to compute, relying only on grid topology information and the results of a standard AC-optimal power flow simulation. The ϕ -metric in particular, defined as the sum of absolute LMP differences across all branches incident to a busbar, proved to be a reliable indicator of splitting potential. The intuition is that a busbar sitting at the boundary of a price zone, with large LMP gradients across multiple connected branches, is exactly the kind of location where rerouting power flows through topological reconfiguration can reduce congestion and lower total generation costs. Moreover, the ζ -metric, the presence of binding voltage constraints, acts as a negative filter, ruling out busbars where splitting would not help.

The main limitation in the results presented in the Chapter and in [20] is that some cost reductions in the exhaustive search came from what is effectively transmission line switching, i.e., disconnecting a branch from the split busbar entirely rather than reassigning it, which the metrics are not designed to detect. This is not necessarily a problem in practice, since line switching and busbar splitting are often managed through the same physical switching apparatus at a substation, but it does mean the metrics may

miss some beneficial configurations. Future work should look at whether ϕ can be adapted to capture this case, and whether the metrics generalise well to more realistic large test cases.

Stochastic topology optimization The motivation for Chapter 5 comes from the observation that grid topology decisions made the day before are locked in at the time of real-time operation, meaning a topology that was optimal under the D-1 forecast may perform poorly if the actual RES output differs significantly. The real offshore wind data used in the Chapter and in [13] illustrates the problem clearly: forecast errors are frequent, sometimes large, and asymmetric in a way that a Gaussian assumption would underestimate. Using a Laplace distribution fitted to the forecast error and generating scenarios via K-means clustering is an approach to limit the curse of dimensionality while still capturing the heavy tails of the error distribution. The number of scenarios W is a key parameter: too few and the optimization is overconfident in the forecast; too many and the problem becomes intractable. The results suggest that 6 to 8 scenarios already capture most of the benefit, though further refinement of the uncertainty quantification methodology could potentially improve performance. The multistep dimension of the model, i.e. optimising the topology over a full 24-hour horizon rather than for a single snapshot, adds practical value because switching actions at substations bring stress to the system, and should therefore be limited if the economic benefit is not extremely clear. The version of the model that allows a limited number of switching actions per day directly reflects this operational reality and produces results close to the fully flexible hourly switching case at much lower computational cost. One important finding is that the scenario-based approach consistently outperforms the deterministic D-1 forecast approach in terms of total costs, even accounting for redispatch at the time of real delivery. This is a non-trivial result because the stochastic model does not know the actual realisation in advance; it simply hedges across scenarios, yet it still finds topologies that are more robust to forecast errors than the deterministic optimum. The AC-OPF feasibility checks on all optimised topologies are also reassuring, since the LPAC relaxation used in the optimization is an approximation and there is always a risk that its solutions are not physically realisable.

Asymmetric bipolar HVDC operation Chapter 6 addresses a scenario that will become increasingly relevant with more extended offshore HVDC grids: a single-pole outage on a full bipolar link, which may persist for days or weeks due to the difficulty of offshore maintenance. In this situation, the two poles of the bipole can carry different power levels, therefore there are asymmetric currents into the grid. The contribution of Chapter 6 is to com-

bine the asymmetric bipolar optimal power flow model (which models the positive, negative and neutral conductors of the bipole explicitly) with the busbar splitting optimization model developed in DIRECTIONS deliverable 1.1. The 15-bus test case is small, but it is sufficient to demonstrate the principle: by separating the two converter poles onto different parts of a split AC busbar, the voltage angle and magnitude constraints that were previously binding become non-binding, giving more room to dispatch generators efficiently. The main limitation of Chapter 6 is the small test case size, which was necessary given the MINLP nature of the problem. Scaling to larger, multi-terminal meshed HVDC systems will require further extensions of the optimization model, and this is the most important direction for future research from this chapter.

General observations All things considered, we believe that the *main finding* of this Deliverable is that busbar splitting yields meaningful cost reductions for only a small subset of locations in any given network, but the savings at those locations can be significant. The pre-screening metrics developed in Chapter 4 directly address this by reducing the search space to a tractable number of candidates without the need for lengthy simulations. The stochastic multistep model in Chapter 5 shows that renewable forecast uncertainty should be accounted for when optimising the topology day-ahead, or when looking for potentially relevant remedial actions. Finally, Chapter 6 further shows that the economic value of topological flexibility can also be exploited under stressed operating conditions, such as a single-pole outage on a bipolar HVDC link. The models developed across all three chapters are useful for system operators to look for new remedial actions in their own network data, planning the operations of future hybrid AC/DC grids with large renewable energy source penetrations.

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Bibliography

- [1] Governments of the countries in the North Sea area, *The Esbjerg Declaration: A Greener and More Sustainable Europe*, [Online] Available: <https://esbjerg.eu/the-esbjerg-declaration>. (accessed March 2, 2026), 18 May 2022.
- [2] Governments of the countries in the North Sea area, *Ostend declaration of energy ministers on The North Seas as Europe's green power plant delivering cross-border projects and anchoring the renewable offshore industry in Europe*, [Online] Available: <https://tinyurl.com/3zzj5tf5>. (accessed February 27, 2026), 24 April 2023.
- [3] Governments of the countries in the North Sea area, *The Hamburg declaration - Building the North Seas' power hub for a resilient and competitive Europe*, [Online] Available: <https://tinyurl.com/4tyfrbjj>. (accessed March 2, 2026), 26 January 2026.
- [4] ENTSO-E, *European offshore network transmission infrastructure needs*, [Online] Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/outlooks/offshore-hub/tyndp-ondp/>. (accessed February 27, 2026).
- [5] Hitachi Energy, *Caithness Moray HVDC Link*, [Online] Available: <https://www.ssen-transmission.co.uk/projects/project-map/caithness—moray/>. (accessed February 27, 2026), 2024.
- [6] Elia Group, *The Princess Elisabeth Island*, [Online] Available: <https://www.elia.be/en/infrastructure-and-projects/infrastructure-projects/princess-elisabeth-island>. (accessed February 27, 2026).
- [7] Danish Energy Agency, *Energy Island in the North Sea*, [Online] Available: <https://ens.dk/en/energy-sources/offshore-wind-power/energy-island-north-sea>. (accessed February 27, 2026).
- [8] Energinet and 50 Hertz, *The green future of offshore wind hubs and hybrid connections*, [Online] Available: <https://bornholmenergyisland.eu/en/> (accessed February 27, 2026).

- [9] G. Bastianel et al., “Review, definition and challenges of electrical energy hubs,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 226, p. 116 258, 2026, ISSN: 1364-0321. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116258>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032125009311>.
- [10] G. Bastianel, C. Hardy, N. Charels, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, “Identification of technical design constraints and considerations for transmission grid expansion planning projects,” *arXiv:2505.05886*, 2025.
- [11] G. Bastianel, M. Vanin, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, “Optimal transmission switching and busbar splitting in hybrid AC/DC grids,” *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, vol. 46, p. 102 182, 2026, ISSN: 2352-4677. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2026.102182>.
- [12] C. K. Jat, J. Dave, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, “Hybrid AC/DC OPF Model for Unbalanced Operation of Bipolar HVDC Grids,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 4987–4997, 2024. DOI: [10.1109/TPWRS.2023.3329345](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2023.3329345).
- [13] G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, H. Ergun, and L. Roald, “Day-ahead transmission grid topology optimization considering renewable energy sources’ uncertainty,” *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 174, p. 111 527, 2026, ISSN: 0142-0615. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2025.111527>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0142061525010750>.
- [14] ENTSO-E, *The reference for the future european electricity system*, [Online] Available: <https://tyndp.entsoe.eu/>. (accessed January 24, 2025).
- [15] C. Coffrin, R. Bent, K. Sundar, Y. Ng, and M. Lubin, “Powermodels.jl: An open-source framework for exploring power flow formulations,” in *Power Systems Computation Conference*, Jun. 2018, pp. 1–8. DOI: [10.23919/PSCC.2018.8442948](https://doi.org/10.23919/PSCC.2018.8442948).
- [16] H. Ergun, J. Dave, D. Van Hertem, and F. Geth, “Optimal power flow for AC–DC grids: Formulation, convex relaxation, linear approximation, and implementation,” *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 2980–2990, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/TPWRS.2019.2897835](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2019.2897835).
- [17] CCR Core TSO Cooperation, *Explanatory document to the Core Capacity Calculation Region methodology for common provisions for regional operational security coordination in accordance with Article 76 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1485*, [Online] Available: <https://acer.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/en/Electricity>. (accessed March 6, 2026), 2019.

- [18] EPRI, *Transmission Topology Optimization, State-of-the-Art White Paper: A GET SET White Paper*, [Online] Available: <https://www.epri.com/research> (accessed July 6, 2025), 2025.
- [19] WATT coalition, *Congestion & overload mitigation with transmission re-configurations*, [Online] Available: <https://www.brattle.com/insights-events/publications/congestion-overload-mitigation-with-transmission-reconfigurations-experience-in-miso-and-spp/> (accessed March 6, 2026), 2022.
- [20] G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, H. Ergun, and L. Roald, *Identifying best candidates for busbar splitting*, arXiv:2510.13000, 2025. arXiv: [2510.13000](https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.13000) [eess.SY].
- [21] C. Coffrin, H. L. Hijazi, K. Lehmann, and P. Van Hentenryck, "Primal and dual bounds for optimal transmission switching," in *2014 PSCC*, 2014, pp. 1–8. doi: [10.1109/PSCC.2014.7038446](https://doi.org/10.1109/PSCC.2014.7038446).
- [22] M. Heidarifar, P. Andrianesis, P. Ruiz, M. C. Caramanis, and I. C. Paschalidis, "An optimal transmission line switching and bus splitting heuristic incorporating AC and N-1 contingency constraints," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 133, p. 107278, 2021, ISSN: 0142-0615. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.107278>.
- [23] B. Morsy, A. Hinneck, D. Pozo, and J. Bialek, "Security constrained OPF utilizing substation reconfiguration and busbar splitting," in *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 212, p. 108507, Nov. 2022, ISSN: 0378-7796. doi: [10.1016/j.epsr.2022.108507](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2022.108507). Accessed: May 12, 2023.
- [24] International Energy Agency, *Electricity grids and secure energy transitions*, [Online] Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/electricity-grids-and-secure-energy-transitions>. (accessed July 3, 2025), 2023.
- [25] European Commission, Joint Research Centre, *Redispatch and congestion management*, [Online] Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/853898>, JRC137685. (accessed July 3, 2025), 2024.
- [26] Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators, *Transmission capacities for cross-zonal trade of electricity and congestion management in the EU*, [Online] Available: <https://www.acer.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/Publications>. (accessed July 6, 2025), 2025.
- [27] N. Shreve, J. Selker, Z. Zimmerman, and R. Doying, *Transmission congestion for 2024*, [Online] Available: https://gridstrategiesllc.com/wp-content/uploads/GS_Transmission-Congestion-for-2024.pdf (accessed February 22, 2026), 2025.

- [28] ENTSO-E transparency platform, *Costs of congestion management*, [Online] Available: <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/congestion-management>. (accessed July 6, 2024).
- [29] SMARD.de, *Congestion management*, [Online] Available: <https://www.smard.de/page/article/5790/214060/congestion-management> (accessed July 6, 2025), 2025.
- [30] N. Shreve, J. Selker, Z. Zimmerman, and R. Gramlich, *2023 transmission congestion report*, [Online] Available: https://gridstrategiesllc.com/wp-content/uploads/Grid-Strategies_2023-Transmission-Congestion-Report.pdf (accessed February 22, 2026), 2024.
- [31] International Energy Agency, *Electricity 2025: Analysis and forecast to 2027*, [Online] Available: <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/0f028d5f-26b1-47ca-ad2a-5ca3103d070a/Electricity2025.pdf>. (accessed July 3, 2025), 2024.
- [32] International Energy Agency, *Building the future transmission grid - strategies to navigate supply chain challenges*, [Online] Available: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules_en. (accessed July 6, 2025), 2025.
- [33] M. Neukirch, "Grinding the grid: Contextualizing protest networks against energy transmission projects in southern germany," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 69, p. 101585, 2020, ISSN: 2214-6296. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101585>.
- [34] ENTSO-E, *Capacity calculation in Core CCR*, [Online] Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/core/explained/>. (accessed July 6, 2025).
- [35] OpenDataElia, *Wind power production estimation and forecast on Belgian grid (Near real-time)*, [Online] Available: <https://opendata.elia.be/explore/dataset/ods086/information/>. (accessed July 7, 2025), 2025.
- [36] H. Heitsch and W. Römisch, "Scenario reduction algorithms in stochastic programming," *Computational Optimization and Applications*, vol. 24, pp. 187–206, 2003. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021805924152>.
- [37] J. M. Morales, A. J. Conejo, and J. Perez-Ruiz, "Economic valuation of reserves in power systems with high penetration of wind power," in *2009 IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting*, 2009.
- [38] J. R. Birge and F. Louveaux, *Introduction to Stochastic Programming*. 2011. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-0237-4>.
- [39] A. Papavasiliou, S. S. Oren, and R. P. O'Neill, "Reserve requirements for wind power integration: A scenario-based stochastic programming framework," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 2197–2206, 2011. DOI: [10.1109/TPWRS.2011.2121095](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2011.2121095).

- [40] A. Papavasiliou and S. S. Oren, "Multiarea stochastic unit commitment for high wind penetration in a transmission constrained network," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 578–592, 2013. DOI: [10.1287/opre.2013.1174](https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.2013.1174).
- [41] L. Devroye and G. Lugosi, "The kernel density estimate," in *Combinatorial Methods in Density Estimation*. New York, NY: Springer New York, 2001, pp. 79–97, ISBN: 978-1-4613-0125-7. DOI: [10.1007/978-1-4613-0125-7_9](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-0125-7_9).
- [42] X. Jin and J. Han, "K-means clustering," in *Encyclopedia of Machine Learning*, C. Sammut and G. I. Webb, Eds. Boston, MA: Springer US, 2010, pp. 563–564, ISBN: 978-0-387-30164-8. DOI: [10.1007/978-0-387-30164-8_425](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-30164-8_425).
- [43] S. Babaeinejadsarookolae and et al., *The power grid library for benchmarking ac optimal power flow algorithms*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.02788>, 2021. arXiv: [1908.02788](https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.02788) [math.OC].
- [44] D. Van Hertem, O. Gomis-Bellmunt, and J. Liang, *HVDC grids for transmission of electrical energy: Offshore grids and a future supergrid*. IEEE Press, 2016.
- [45] S. Hardy, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "A Techno-Economic Analysis of meshed Topologies of Offshore Wind HVAC Transmission," in *2021 IEEE Madrid PowerTech*, 2021, pp. 1–6. DOI: [10.1109/PowerTech46648.2021.9494784](https://doi.org/10.1109/PowerTech46648.2021.9494784).
- [46] D. Van Hertem et al., "Substations for Future HVDC Grids: Equipment and Configurations for Connection of HVDC Network Elements," *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 56–66, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/MPE.2019.2909006](https://doi.org/10.1109/MPE.2019.2909006).
- [47] TenneT, *2 GW program*, [Online] Available: <https://www.tennet.eu/about-tennet/innovations/2gw-program>. (accessed February 27, 2026).
- [48] J. Serrano-Sillero, M. Ángeles Moreno, and A. Morales, "HVDC grids with heterogeneous configuration stations under DC asymmetrical operation," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 113, pp. 449–460, 2019, ISSN: 0142-0615. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2019.05.053>.
- [49] O. Damanik, G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, *Security-Constrained AC/DC Grid Optimal Power Flow Considering Asymmetrical HVDC Grid Operation using Sparse Tableau Formulation*, 2025. arXiv: [2511.10335](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.10335) [eess.SY].

BIBLIOGRAPHY

etch.be

